

Artem BARATIUK,
Postgraduate Student, Assistant at the
Department of Psychodiagnostics and Clinical Psychology,
Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv
Email: bergmanartem@knu.ua
ORCID: [0000-0003-3473-0434](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3473-0434)

The Phenomenon of Digital Dissociation after Prolonged Immersion in Virtual Environments

Digital dissociation is a transient or persistent state of post-virtual disintegration that follows intensive or prolonged immersion in a digital environment and disrupts cognitive integration, affective resonance, and bodily identity. Requests for help with atypical symptom profiles are becoming more frequent, yet the boundaries with digital fatigue, cognitive overload, depersonalization, and attention disturbances remain indistinct, which-absent a stable categorical framework and measurement tools-complicates therapeutic and preventive decisions.

Objective. To theoretically substantiate the phenomenon as a distinct construct with an internal structure and specific psychophysiological and behavioral manifestations-drawing on phenomenological psychology, cognitive neuroscience, digital anthropology, and the post-structuralist critique of identity-and to develop a three-level diagnostic model with operationalized criteria for subsequent empirical validation.

In contemporary discourse, interest is growing in alterations of identity, cognitive coherence, and presence during digital interaction. Evidence points to identity splitting with functional decoupling of the digital self from physical identity, heightened impulsivity, and reduced reflective self-control [3]. This is consonant with the notion of a split subjectivity in the hyperreality of avatars, masks, and simulacra, where the self loses a stable ontological core and persists in perceptual instability [6]. Unlike trauma-associated states, digital dissociation emerges as a response to interface

Note: This preprint is an English translation of the conference paper originally published in Ukrainian:

Baratiuk, A. (2025). Fenomen tsyfrovoyi disotsiatsii pislia tryvaloho perebuвання u virtualnomu seredovishchi [The Phenomenon of Digital Dissociation after Prolonged Immersion in a Virtual Environment]. In Science, Technology, Innovation: Vectors of Transformation: Materials of the Scientific and Practical Conference (Uzhhorod, Ukraine, October 24-25, 2025, pp. 115-119). *Molodyi Vchenyi*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17524579>

overload, deficits of sensory feedback, and delayed bodily self-sensing, which co-occur with temporal fragmentation of subjective experience and a disturbance of the unity of time, space, and sensation [5].

Phenomenology describes a loss of bodily rootedness, while cognitive science and the global neuronal theory of consciousness link perceptual integration to inter-network synchronization, which becomes disrupted under conditions of digital overload. Neurofunctionally, one observes de-coordination between prefrontal structures-particularly the anterior cingulate cortex (ACC)-and limbic and associative regions, foremost the posterior cingulate cortex (PCC) within the Default Mode Network (DMN), alongside reduced connectivity along ACC-thalamus-central operculum trajectories and a weakening of attentional and emotional control. In parallel, disrupted PCC coupling with the lateral temporal cortex may indicate instability of the identity model in digital contexts [2].

Sensory deprivation in VR-marked by deficits in haptics, thermal, and proprioceptive signals-shifts bodily presence and likely suppresses somatosensory integration circuits. EEG tends to show increased synchronization in the alpha, beta, and gamma bands, together with a blurring of bodily sensation, diminished self-awareness, and depersonalization, findings consistent with reduced intermodal (cross-modal) integration required for the embodied self [4].

At the psychosocial level, there is blurring of referent identity and self-forgetting, with attentional capture by the avatar, mask, or profile. In the virtual mirror, reward is modulated by dopaminergic pathways of the medial nucleus accumbens, activated by systems of immediate reinforcement, excessive D3R activation is associated with reduced affective sensitivity and a state of inner emptiness, wherein external activity fails to elicit a commensurate emotional response [1].

The generalized model encompasses three interrelated levels-cognitive, affective, and somato-perceptual-which together form a single diagnostic configuration with a post-virtual trajectory ranging from transient to persistent (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Conceptual model of the structure of digital dissociation

The cognitive level describes a breakdown of attentional focus with fragmentation of the perceptual-thinking field and heightened susceptibility to interface distractions, it also entails slowed switching between the rule sets of virtual and physical environments, observable as increased goal re-engagement latency, reduced accuracy on dual-context tasks, and the carryover of virtual heuristics into offline behavior. The affective level is marked by emotional leveling after interaction, diminished reactivity and experiential richness, and a sustained, palpable sense of inner emptiness, while frequent difficulties in recognizing and verbalizing one's own states indicate a secondary alexithymic tendency. The somato-perceptual level encompasses a transient shift in embodiment, blunting of bodily sensitivity, and a discretization of time and space that leads to untimely motor and visuospatial decisions in the real environment.

The central node of post-virtual disintegration is sustained by three mechanisms—switching rigidity, affective hyporesonance, and somato-perceptual misalignment of embodiment—whose coupling strength is modulated by the intensity and duration of immersion, by sensory poverty or overload, and by individual self-regulation. Operationalization rests on four criteria: an asymmetry of reality perception with the dominance of online sets during offline interaction, post-virtual cognitive disorientation with slowed recovery of focus and perseveration of maladaptive rules,

an alexithymic tendency characterized by difficulty identifying and labeling feelings despite preserved intellectual description, and an increasing need for real grounding through brief bodily-sensory rituals. The threshold of detection is defined as at least two criteria drawn from different levels that persist for more than 30-60 minutes and are accompanied by minimal everyday dysfunction, this frame differentiates the phenomenon from digital fatigue, depersonalization disorder, and non-digital attention disturbances.

The diagnostic cluster corresponds to the three-level map of the phenomenon and serves as the basis for subsequent validation through the combination of behavioral indicators of switching, brief affect-labeling probes, and somato-perceptual embodiment tests under controlled procedures.

The proposed model is a theoretical construct that requires empirical validation. Future research should focus on experimental verification of neurophysiological correlates using EEG and fMRI, on the development of a standardized diagnostic battery, and on examining how the type and duration of virtual interaction shape symptom expression. Theoretical analysis systematically delineates digital dissociation as a distinct form of transient disruption of psychic integration following intensive or prolonged presence in VR, with a tri-component organization-cognitive, affective, and somato-perceptual-that forms a dynamic model of fragmentation of the digital self. The model explains post-virtual disintegration through de-coordination of prefrontal and limbic structures, sensory deprivation, dispersion of identity in the virtual mirror, and chronic hyperstimulation of dopaminergic mechanisms, and it proposes four interrelated diagnostic criteria that ensure differentiation from adjacent phenomena and provide a foundation for empirical diagnostics and further validation, including behavioral testing, neurophysiological monitoring, and psychopreventive protocols for education, work, and digital therapy.

References

Note: This preprint is an English translation of the conference paper originally published in Ukrainian.

1. Enriquez-Traba, J., Arenivar, M., Yarur-Castillo, H., Noh, C., Flores, R., Weil, T., Roy, S., Usdin, T., LaGamma, C., Wang, H., Tsai, V., Kerspern, D., Moritz, A., Sibley, D., Lutas, A., Moratalla, R., Freyberg Z., Tejada H. Dissociable control of motivation and reinforcement by distinct ventral striatal dopamine receptors. *Nature neuroscience*. 2024. Vol. 28. pp. 105-121. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41593-024-01819-9>.
2. Garg, H., Sharan, P., Kumaran, S., Bhargava, R., Patra B., Tripathi M. MRI Analysis of Dissociative Convulsions: A Case-Controlled Study. *Neurology India*. 2023. Vol. 71. pp. 476-486. URL: <https://doi.org/10.4103/0028-3886.378651>.
3. González-Padilla, P., Hernández-Tamurejo Á, Debasa F. The dissociation of user identity and behaviour in the real world versus the virtual world: a review. *ESIC Market*. 2025. Vol. 59. pp. 1-22. URL: <https://doi.org/10.7200/esicm.56.399>.
4. Menicucci, D., Cesari, V., Cipriani, E., Piarulli A., Gemignani A. Sleep Deprivation Induces Acute Dissociation via Altered EEG Rhythms Expression and Connectivity. *bioRxiv*. 2022. pp. 1-40. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.03.21.485177>.
5. Ricci, V., Maina G., Martinotti G. Dissociation and Temporality in Substance Abuse: A Clinical Phenomenological Overview. *Psychopathology*. 2023. Vol. 57. pp. 219-228. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1159/000533862>.
6. Tripathi R. Fragmented Selves: Identity, Consciousness and Reality in the Digital Age. *Open Access Journal of Data Science and Artificial Intelligence*. 2024. Vol. 2. pp. 1-6. URL: <https://doi.org/10.23880/oajda-16000148>.